

Archaeology of Prakṛti:

Excavating the Lost Myth & Theology of the Goddess Religions

Dr Tamal Dasgupta

Abstract: This article stems forth from the research need, that in spite of the prolific archaeological evidence of pre-historic female figurines from Pandu Rajar Dhibi to Chandraketurgarh in early Bengal, little or nothing is known about these archaic cults of the feminine. As a response, this article attempts to reconstruct the theology and myth of the religions of the archaic feminine/goddess cults, by connecting the dots between archaeological discoveries of the female figurines and the potentially corresponding scriptural sources and folk traditions, thus recovering the lost myths of such figurines. This article's title, "Archaeology of Prakṛti" alludes to Bankim Chandra Chatterjee's proposition that in Bengal, there is the religion and culture built around Prakṛti of Tantra and Sāṃkhya, where the first cause of creation of universe (Jagadkāraṇa), the primordial (Ādyā), eternal (Nityā), mysteriously unspeakable (Avyaktā) source of creation, i.e. Prakṛti is popularly worshipped as the Mother Goddess. This article goes beyond Sāṃkhya/Tantra to conduct type studies of the cultic figurines, by investigating relevant texts from ancient India and the lived traditions of goddess cults where archaic remnants are distinctly present, to trace the lost trajectories of myth and theology of the feminine.

Keywords: Female Figurines, Harappa & Mohenjodaro, Mātrkā, Prakṛti, Jagadkāraṇa, Sāṃkhya, Śakti, Śākta, Bengal, Bengali, Goddess Idols, Mother Goddess, Ūṣā, Pṛthvī, Ten-Armed Goddess, Daśāyudhā, Durgā, Kālī, Śrī Śrī Caṇḍī, Mahābhārata, Pandu Rajar Dhibi (PRD), Chandraketurgarh (CKG), Gangaridai/Gangaridae, Pancacūḍā, Yakṣī, Serpent/Nāga Goddess, Valāka/ Valākinī/ Beaked/Bird Goddess, Khecari, Vidyādhari, Dākinī, One-Horned Goddess, Ekaśṛṅgā, Ekānamśā, Śrī/Lakṣmī, Dhānyamatsyā, Śaṣṭhī, Vrata/Vrātya, Mother Figurine with Child, Tārā, Veda, Tantra.

One

The archaic goddess idols, or the female figurines (in case some scholars resist the term goddess) which were surely used for cultic/ritual purposes, are a recurring motif in our archaeology for many millennia, during which Indian subcontinent underwent many upheavals, the great chalcolithic civilization of Harappa-Mohenjodaro came to an end (1900 BC), and the next epicentre of civilization arose in the east, in the form of the so-called "second wave of urbanization" (600 BC). In spite of this very large interregnum when archaeological finds are very sparse, after a gap of a millennium and half, we witness the resurfacing of female figurine again, as if eastern Indian cults of the (divine) feminine tantalizingly bore a legacy of the Harappan cults. Cultic female figurines are found in the Harappan civilization, in Pandu Rajar Dhibi (PRD) of Bengal (contemporaneous with the late Harappan phase), and after a gap of 1500 years (approx.), we again find such female figurines in eastern India, in Magadh, as well as the Chandraketurgarh (CKG) Gangaridai civilization, with distinct iconographic patterns. In the absence of any written records, the theology and myth of these archaic female figurines remain a puzzle, though.

Take for example the familiar iconography of the female figurine with elaborate headgear, with radiating crests/beams/arrows/petals in Her maṇḍala. We find such idols in the Harappan world, and we find such idols again in the Magadhan world after 1500 years, Her myth is not known. It will remain unknown till we do not find any corresponding document to illuminate Her iconographic symbolism. This is obvious to note that Her iconography undergoes changes from the Harappan period to the Magadhan period. Eventually in the Gangaridai era, the radiating structures turn into miniscule weapons, often numbering ten (refer to the cover image of this issue of JBS), as we see a Daśāyudhā or ten-armed goddess. Would this be a template for the emergence of the cult of the ten-armed goddess?

Fig.1: [Harappan figurines](#) 4500 years ago approx. (above) Fig 2: [Magadhan Figurines](#) 1400 years ago approx. (below).

Fig.3: [Gangaridai Era Figurines](#) 1200 years ago (approx.)

This is curious to note that the Earth Goddess or Pṛthvī is explicitly attributed ten arms, while Ūṣā or the Dawn Goddess is also specifically considered to have ten-arms in two different Ṛg Vedic sūktas (Bhattacharya 259), which might be significant in our attempt to reconstruct the archaic myth of the Goddess, particularly in the absence of any coherent written records of the evolution or chronology of the rise of goddess cults. Sukumar Sen points out that Goddess Ūṣā's Bodhan/Invocation was a unique ceremony (not performed to other deities) which was a ritual during autumn as per Ṛg Vedic hymns, and Sen considers it to be the forerunner of the Autumnal Invocation (Śāradīya Bodhan) of Goddess Durgā (*Probandho Sonkolon* 319).

That the Goddess Ūṣā did not originally belong to the (overtly patriarchal) Vedic pantheon, and instead hailed from the non-Vedic world of Harappan civilization, and that the Ṛgveda actually documents Indra's brutal attack on the Goddess Ūṣā, this line of argument was cogently forwarded by D D Kosambi, and following him, Debiprasad Chattopadhyay reiterates this hypothesis with lengthy reasonings (66-69).

A Dawn Goddess's myth would probably indicate that the radiating arrows in her iconography stand for the rays of light. However, the many radiating rays might also symbolise the different components radiating out of Prakṛti (in Sāṃkhya there are a total of 24 components of Prakṛti, which together come to form the whole of the animate and inanimate universes). Once these rays turn into weapons, She can be a War Goddess as well. Indian wars often began at daybreak, so the Dawn Goddess could also be a War Goddess.

Dawn Goddess can very well symbolise the first cause of creation. She *is* the first cause of a new day. Further, the Earth Goddess/ Pṛthvī is called the ultimate source of creation, current flourish, and ultimate destruction of the universe (sṛṣṭisthitilaya) in a śloka from *Atharva Veda*, that is, the creator, nurturer and destroyer of the world, as observed by Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya (259).

Such a scriptural statement essentially leads to the monistic theology of a Great Goddess, as always attested by early figurines which suggest the sovereignty and singularity of the Goddess. She is no consort to any male God. Indeed, all the ancient plaques and figurines we investigate in this article do imply such a monistic theology of the Goddess where She is no consort, and She has no consort either.

Further, archaeologist Gautam Sengupta observes in his brief article “Bangalir Durgā” that the miniscule weapons found as hair pins in the elaborate headgear of the Chandraketugarh figurine are still found in the hands of Goddess Durgā today: arrow, axe, goad (or elephant goad), thunderbolt, trident.

There are usually four attendants with this female figurine, and this is again seen as a steady feature of the goddess Durgā’s maṇḍala since the middle ages. While this is true that the earliest Durgā idols from the Pāla period do not have four attendants, but at this time, the iconography is heavily coming from the Southern India (Pāla intermarriages with Rāṣṭrakūṭa might have played a role). A common form of the maṇḍala of Goddess Tārā during the Pāla period had four attendants, Sukumar Sen observes (197). Further, a motif of goat sacrifice with music of drum (dhāk) is seen in one 200 BC CKG plaque. This is practised in Sandhi Pūjā of Goddess Durgā to this day, which is a striking parallel.

Fig. 4: [Chandraketugarh: Goat Sacrifice and Drum Beating in Cultic Worship of Female Figurine](#)

[Fig.5: Chandraketugarh. 200 BC \(approx.\) Female Figurine with four attendants \(Renzo Freschi Oriental Art Gallery, Milan\)](#)

[Fig 6: Tantric Buddhist Goddess Tārā with four attendants \(18th century Tibetan Thangka\)](#)

Interestingly, ladies' hairpins were a prolific feature at Mohenjodaro, as Atul Sur observes in *Sindhu Sabhyatar Swarupa O Samasya* (37). Therefore, the sacred symbolism inherent in the iconography of the cultic figurines of Daśāyudhā might have stemmed from the mundane world, in a gesture of monism. The Mother Goddess monistically unites the sacred and the profane, the mysterious and the mundane.

Two: The Buffalo Slayer

Harappan civilization had buffalo sacrifice as an important ritual practice. Asko Parpola believes that such buffalo sacrifice rituals were religiously cognate with similar bull sacrifice rituals elsewhere in the contemporary world (Parpola mostly speaks about such rituals in West Asia), and he maintains that the cult of the Goddess Durgā would eventually stem from this Harappan practice, where many centuries later the sacrificial buffalo would undergo anthropomorphic evolution and would become the buffalo demon, as Parpola contends (241).

Fig 7: [Harappan Buffalo Sacrifice](#)

Strikingly, two millennia after the dissolution of the Harappan civilization, the first buffalo slayer goddess figurines emerge in the subcontinent, sometime around first century BC. Again, we do not find the myth behind such early buffalo slayer idols, wherein the goddess slays the buffalo by using bare hands. We also find idols where the goddess uses a spear/trident to slay the buffalo. Such idols should not be designated mahiṣāsūramardinī, as the buffalo is not the same as the buffalo demon. Such idols are mahiṣamardinī, or buffalo slayer.

Fig 8: [Buffalo Slaying Goddess \(Mathura 200 CE\)](#). LACMA Exhibit says this is “Durgā Slaying the Buffalo Demon”.

[Fig 9: Goddess Slaying Buffalo \(Seventh Century\). Victoria and Albert Museum somehow incorrectly calls this idol Durgā Mahisāsūramardīnī](#)

The first recorded myth of the buffalo demon comes from *Śrī Śrī Caṇḍī* of the *Mārkaṇḍeya Purāṇa*. *Śrī Śrī Caṇḍī* is a later interpolation into the said Purāṇic text. Many scholars maintain that *Śrī Śrī Caṇḍī* was composed in the sixth century, sometime around 550 CE. [Note](#)

[Fig 8: In the seventh century we get to see the Mamallapuram rock relief of lion-riding goddess Durgā slaying an anthropomorphic buffalo demon.](#)

While the Goddess who kills the buffalo demon has a distinct Purāṇic theology, and follows the usual template of war with numerous such demons/asuras, and as such is at the heart of the popular worship of the Great Goddess, it is pertinent to note here that we do not find any mythical and theological explanations of, or the story behind the iconography of the original motif of the buffalo slaying goddess. Her dhyānamantra or iconological chant is lost. All existing chants relate to the Purāṇic goddess who kills the buffalo demon.

What was the mythical story behind the original goddess who was slaying the buffalo? This goddess must have been popular, because we have numerous plaques and idols of this mahiṣamardinī goddess. Surely such a standard iconography had a celebrated narrative. Nevertheless, the continuity of lived tradition is striking, as some scholars notice. “The Harappan seal depicts the ritual slaughter of a buffalo by the use of a sharp, spike-like instrument, and the (Durgā) iconography shows the Goddess killing the buffalo demon with a trident or a spear” (Rupendrakumar Chattopadhyay et al 129).

Interestingly, when we first witness the buffalo-slaying goddess, 100 BC approximately, around the same time, in the Roman empire, the Mithraic mysteries depicted God Mithras ritually slaying a bull. Even the Mithraic mysteries did not leave behind sufficient written narratives, so reconstruction of the theology of our similar sacrificial iconography puts up a challenge.

The Durgāstotra of Arjuna in Mahābhārata calls the Goddess “mahīṣārṅkriye nityaṃ”, that is, forever fond of buffalo-blood (Rupendrakumar Chattopadhyay et al 131), which strongly alludes to a cult of animal sacrifice, which variously can signify fertility rites, propitiation of a ferocious goddess, symbolic unity of life and death, oneness of creation and destruction in the iconology of the goddess, cycle of life and death, festival of meat eating, the ritual slaughter of a sacred animal in the hands of the goddess. Also, the antiquity of the autumnal festival of blood sacrifice is attested in one translated biography of Hieun Tsiang, where the bandits of Ayodhya are said to offer a human sacrifice to Goddess Durgā during autumn (Rupendrakumar Chattopadhyay et al 131)

The sublime terror of this iconography may easily connect it to the primordial matter of Prakṛti. Ambivalent, ferocious, casual, deep and close: this is no remote, abstract god promising a pie in the sky. There is a lasting immediacy in this iconography, which makes it both primitive and eternal. From the cult of this buffalo-slayer goddess, eventually the rise of the Great Goddess can be witnessed in Devī Māhātmya where “She is represented as the ultimate source of the universe, and as the ultimate source she is called Mūlaprakṛti (originant)” (Shin 74). What is more fascinating, at least two distinctly different religious traditions, one of the radiant dawn and another of the buffalo sacrifice, which might or might not have been interconnected in the Harappan world, may have come together to form the Great Goddess tradition of Śākta Tantra during the historical era. This amalgamation shows a theological trend towards monism.

[Fig 9: Buffalo Slaying Goddess, Third Century CE](#)

[Fig 10: Buffalo Slaying Goddess Idol, found on the riverbank of Damodar, Bardhaman, West Bengal](#)

Three: The Bird Goddess

The beaked female figurine or bird goddess was the presiding deity in the chalcolithic archaeological complex called Pandu Rajar Dhibi (PRD) in the Bardhaman district of modern-day West Bengal, as attested by the excavation report of Paresh Chandra Dasgupta. The earliest stratum of this archaeological site was contemporaneous with the final stage of Harappan civilization (4000 years before present), the mature phase might have been burned down in an aggressive attack by outsiders, sometime around 3000 years before present, as Paresh Chandra Dasgupta observes.^{[Note](#)}

I argued in a Bengali article titled “Bangalir Bismrito Otit” published in *Shoptodina* (Vol 9 No 2 2023) in favour of using certain scriptural parallels to illuminate our archaeological understanding of the culture, society, religion and civilization of PRD.

Fig 11: The Beaked/Bird Goddess of Pandu Rajar Dhibi (left). Taken from Paresh Chandra Dasgupta's book, *The Excavations at Pandu Rajar Dhibi* (right).

Various bird (beaked) goddess figurines were present in the Harappan civilization, so the beaked goddess of PRD forms a continuum with the similar cultic idols of mature IVC. It is interesting to observe here that not only in PRD, but similar beaked female figurines were found from other archaeological sites of West Bengal too, which can be seen in the West Bengal State Archaeological Directorate's publication containing images of early terracotta idols from Bengal titled *Eloquent Earth*. Two such images are produced below.

Fig 12. Beaked Female Figurines are found in various archaeological sites (2000-1000 BC) of West Bengal.

From *Eloquent Earth*, published by West Bengal State Archaeological Directorate.

The iconography of the bird goddess connects to the rise of the Goddess Kālī, who is called a bird (valākīnī) during the Purāṇic period, in Kālidāsa's poetry, in *Kumārasambhava* as well as *Raghuvamśa* (Sasibhusan Dasgupta 65). Goddess Kālī has fifteen manifestations called nityās or eternal, and one of them is valākā or bird, as per Kulacūḍāmaṇi Tantra, as I have discussed in my Bengali article “Ma Kālīr Utthan” in Shoptodina (Vol 6 No 1 2020).

Also, the goddess Vagalāmukhī in the Daśamahāvidyā pantheon was originally a bird goddess as her etymology suggests (Valākā means bird, Vagalā/Bagulā stands for a crane), and this is one of the informed positions on the origin of this goddess critically expounded by Jae-Eun Shin, and even some of the existing iconographies associate Her image with a crane or variously with a crow, a parrot, a duck and an owl, as Shin goes on to observe (87). The goddess is still worshipped in bird-faced forms, though not in Bengal, where the mainstream Daśamahāvidyā pantheon shows her as a beautiful goddess, a devī who holds the tongue of a demon in one hand, as the other hand raises a club to beat the demon.

Birds are often crucial members in the maṇḍalas of multiple goddesses, Kālī's maṇḍala having a crane, Cāmuṇḍā's having an owl, Dhumāvātī's having a raven, and so on. Jae-Eun Shin repeatedly emphasizes the significance of the bird motif in the early goddess cults. A group of fearsome *Mātr̥s* are mentioned in *Matsya Purāṇa*, and some of them are prominent bird deities: Vinatā (bird grasper), Ulkāmukhī (Owl faced), Ayomukhī (Iron beaked) (Shin 71). Śalyaparva of *Mahābhārata* mentions the mātṛgaṇa, group of mothers who have many forms (nānārūpa), and we find the bird mothers there: Kākī, Vinatā, Pūtanā are bird goddesses. (Shin 83) Many of these *Mātr̥s* were later subsumed into the figures of the yoginīs. A Tantra text from twelfth century, *Kaulajñānanirṇaya* “says that when Devī asks Śiva about how the yoginīs wander on earth, Śiva lists a number of forms they would assume. Specially mentioned among birds are a dove, vulture, swan, owl and crane” (Shin 83). Shin produces a list of bird faced yoginīs from Skanda Purāṇa where we witness Krauñcī (curlew), Kapotikā (dove), Ulūkikā (owl), Sukī (parrot), Śyenī (hawk)” (84). Sukumar Sen observes in his *Great Goddesses* that the Goddess has “some ornithomorphic names” in *Harivamśa* out of which he lists Śakuni (Vulture) and Pūtanā (Stork) (29). Interestingly Pūtanā, a bird goddess who is mentioned as such in Śalya Parva of *Mahābhārata*, would later become a monstrous villain in the narratives of the baby Kṛṣṇa in *Viṣṇupurāṇa* and *Bhāgavatapurāṇa*, as Vaiṣṇavism/Orthodox Hinduism would eventually vilify the cult of the bird mother goddess. While such mother cults had enough potentials of fearful ambivalence already (Hārītī, Goddess from later Buddhist Tantra is a case in point), the monstrous othering of the bird mother cult might have resulted in its decimation.

One of the crucial characteristics of Dākīnīs and Vidyādhārīs who are flying attendants to the Goddess is that they have, in Shin's words, an “aerial ability” (83). Khecarī mudrā in yoga has nothing explicitly to do with birds, and yet the name might suggest a deep-rooted unconscious memory of bird cults in our religious palimpsest. In Chandraketurgarh, we do find a popular winged figurine (image below).

Fig 13. [Winged Figurine, CKG Gangaridai Civilization. 200 BC approx., Berlin Ethnological Museum](#)

A tradition of bird worship might have been hinted at the śloka of Aitareya Āraṇyaka, “Vayāṃsi Vamgavagadhāśceraṇpādāḥ” which is the first recorded mention of Vanga/Banga in Vedic literature, which might indicate the bird totem worship by the early Bengali people. Atul Sur in his *Bangla O Bangalir Biborton* considered that early Bengalis were worshippers of the Bird totem (21).

How does the bird goddess symbolise the theology of Prakṛti, the primordial, eternal, unspeakable principle of creation? Parallels can be drawn between the nocturnal bird, and the primordial night of creation. Further, we can see multiple Purāṇic references to the creation of the universe in the form of an egg, or aṇḍa, where the created universe is repeatedly referred to as brahmāṇḍa, or the egg born of the unknown principle of creation (brahma), e.g. *Brahmāṇḍa Purāṇa*. This might suggest that the original cosmogony of the bird goddess might have hailed her as the mother of the universe, and considered the universe to be born out of her egg.

Further, bird clans were closely connected with sky deities, as confirmed by the Purāṇic stories of Aruṇa and Garuḍha. The initial clash of Garuḍha with the Vedic and Purāṇic gods in heaven and his eventual taming by Viṣṇu probably signify that such bird cults after a period of hostility were appropriated and subsumed within Purāṇic Hinduism. The bird in its flight may also symbolise the ultimate flight of the soul, or nirvāṇa/kaivalya/mokṣa, which might have been signified by the bird goddess. *Niddesa* (3rd Century BC), a Pali text, attests that crows were worshipped in ancient India. Crows still play a role in Hindu funeral rites where the bird is offered the final meal meant for a departed soul. It is pertinent to remember that Goddess Kālī is hailed as the bestower of kaivalya (Kālī Kaivalyadāyinī). Kaivalya

literally means oneness, but in context, this is akin to salvation. Nocturnal birds can symbolise the night, the darkness out of which the universe was born. In Vedic cosmogony, often the dawn and the night are considered to be sisters, and dawn follows night, and it is night which is the source of creation, and dawn too is created from night. Sukumar Sen emphasizes the significance of the goddess of night (*Probondho Sonkolon* 129). The beaked female figurines might have represented a nocturnal bird, symbolising the primordial night of creation, and also the dark night of destruction. An ambivalence is possible. We may refer to the beaked figurines which looked like a grim skull, and which might have embodied the magical, shamanic religions of the ambivalent goddess of life and death, whom some scholars claim to have found in the Harappan figurines: “a grim embodiment of the mother-goddess who is also the guardian of the dead – an underworld deity connected like with the corpse and the seed-corn buried beneath the earth” (qtd. in Debiprasad Chattopadhyaya *Bharatiya Darshan* 72).

Goddess Kālī’s connection with this bird figurine (repeated mentions of Valākā, or the bird, adorn the hymns of Kālī in *Brihad Tantrasāra* of Agambāgīśa) hints that at least part of Her theology might have come from the bird goddess. Here, let us also remember the cultic figurine on a sacred tree, for whom animal sacrifice used to be carried out in Harappa-Mohenjodaro. While the figurine on the pipal tree might be a forerunner of the later cults of the yakṣa, and we shall turn to that soon, but this could also be associated with the bird cults, as a bird deity is likely to be venerated on a tree. In Bengali fairy tales, old and wise birds like Byangoma-Byangomi speak and predict future, on a banyan tree, at nightfall.

Fig 14. [Harappan Seal](#) of a tree deity, before whom animal sacrifice is offered. The seven figures are considered to be precursors of the seven mothers or saptamātrkā by some scholars. 2500 BC approx..

A Night Deity was mentioned in Ṛgveda as Nakt, and as Kṛṣṇī (the dark girl), Sukumar Sen observes in his *The Great Goddesses of the Indic Tradition*: Aditi, the ancient mother of gods is likened to this night; night/Nakt is the body of Aditi as a speckled cow (16). There are many dawns, depending on the season of the year, Sen further observes here, so Ūṣā has plural appearances, but night is an eternal constant that does not change (16). This brings us very close to the concept of the creator goddess as

nityā, or eternal. Needless to say, as Nakt transforms to Ūṣā, night changes to dawn, it implies a primordial creator goddess of night transforming into a dazzling dawn goddess of the created splendour. This might help us connect to the philosophy of Prakṛti as night, as the primordial night of creation, in other words, ādyā nityā avyaktā jagadkāraṇa who would give birth to the created world represented by dawn. Interestingly Sukumar Sen mentions in the same vein that night can also be ambiguous, and can be a demoness in some of the old folklores of the Indo-European speech communities (17).

Fig 15. [Grim Figurine from Harappan civilization. 2500 BC approx.. From author's album.](#)

Veneration of the night as well as dread of the night can be seen as the ambivalent features of the Rātri Sūkta of Ṛgveda, However, no verse of Ṛgveda offers any libation to female deities, including the very important ones devoted to Ūṣā and Saraswatī, a fact noticed by Sukumar Sen in his *Great Goddesses*. Nevertheless, we notice that the night continues to be an integral aspect of the worship of the great goddess. The unitary monism of night is a theological principle in the popular rituals of Tantra. Theology of the primal night unites life and death, creation and destruction, light and darkness, matter and spirit, time and space, humans and non-humans alike. Kathleen Erndl observes: “Implicit in this Goddess theology is a kind of monism in which matter and spirit are not differentiated but are a continuity subsumed within śakti, the dynamic feminine creative principle (Erndle Ch.1).

Four: The Serpent Goddess

While Serpent worship or Nāga cults were extremely important in ancient India, there is only one seal of serpent worship, the so-called serpent queen seal that we find in the Harappan civilization. In Chandraketugarh (CKG) we have found a few plaques and figurines which could be identified with the serpent cults. The serpent goddesses of antiquity might have signified plenitude and abundance, fertility, rain, water, subterranean magic; while the (much later) Tantric concept of Kuṇḍalinī might contain elements from the early theology and philosophy of the serpent goddess.

Scholars have argued that in ancient India Nāga worship constituted a major religion, and it was later subsumed within a plethora of other emerging religions including Buddhism, Jainism, Vaishnavism, Shaivism etc. Scholars of Mahābhārata have consistently noticed the significance of the Nāga cults in its textual memory.

Fig 16. [Serpent Seal, Harappan Civilization](#)

Many centuries later Bengal would witness the emergence of Manasā cult. The theology and myth of the Serpent Goddess would be encapsulated in the Mangalakāvya. The stories of Manasā Mangala suggest a seafaring past, radically different from the insular middle ages. Large maritime activities were the hallmark of the CKG Gangaridai civilization. Serpent Goddess plaques from CKG archaeological complex might have stood for a glorious past. Back in the days of PRD (1500 BC approx.), Bengal's seafarers might have interacted with similar serpent goddess cults in the Aegean (the Crete Island serpent goddess idol i.e. [Minoan Snake Goddess](#) could be a point of reference as a seal from Crete island was found in PRD according to Paresh Chandra Dasgupta's Excavation Report).

Fig 17. [Lady with Serpent Insignia, CKG: Serpent Goddess?](#)

Fig 18. [Serpent Goddess? CKG. 200 BC approx. Now in Met Museum](#)

The ancient cult of the snake goddess could have possibly included a) wealth, as texts often associate serpent worship with subterranean treasures, hidden riches, fulfilment of desire through dynamic mobilization of natural, cultural and occult resources; b) magical herbs, remedies and medicines as the serpent cults might have practised shamanic cures; c) mystic quests for self-realization in the form of Kuṇḍalinī Tantra where the most important vital force of the human body; the Kuṇḍalinī, is imagined to be a serpent; d) an ancient culture and civilization that figuratively (and to some extent literally) went underground owing to Vedic and Purāṇic onslaught; e) primordial feminine principles of creation like earth and water; f) fertility principle of monsoon season, which is the season of serpent worship, when lush vegetations signalled plenitude for Bengali people; g) nocturnal source of the creation of the universe; h) a localised guardian deity in the form of a resident serpent (bastu shaap in colloquial Bengali), which resides underneath human residence: which is large and poisonous, but still benign and protective, as per lived traditions; i) narrative healing, as most snakes are not poisonous, but people die often because of fearful shock, so the serpent cult might have helped people through a psychological assurance of goddess narratives, in the frequent eventuality of snake-bites; j) symbolic association with sacred plants, i.e. Manasā (*Euphorbia neriifolia*) and PhaniManasā (*Opuntia ficus-indica*), deemed to be manifestations of the serpent goddess, and thus exhibiting an ancient Indian religious custom of the worship of an arboreal deity.

Nityā is mentioned in Bengali Manasā ballads as the elder sister and guardian to the Serpent Goddess Manasā, as Sukumar Sen observes in his article “Mahādevī Nityā” (17). Nityā is also one of the epithets for Prakṛti, which means eternal. Further, Nityā occurs as one of the epithets of the great Goddess in

Mārkaṇḍeya Purāṇa, as Sen points out in his *Great Goddesses* ((36). Thus, Nityā might illuminate the archaic theology of the serpent goddess, as this term signifies eternity and immortality, most likely through a dialectical process of the cult of the deadly serpent. The nectar of immortality could form a unitary and monistic wholeness with poison, under the auspice of the Serpent Goddess.

There are ample scopes for identification between the serpent goddess and the wealth goddess, as Sukumar Sen maintains in *Great Goddesses* (49). Indeed, we notice that in Bengali popular culture, Manasā is called Viṣalakṣmī or the poison Lakṣmī. Padmā is a common epithet which is applied to both the goddesses Lakṣmī and Manasā, and both have their abode on the lotus, i.e. Padmālaya. Trunk of the elephant was likened to a serpent in ancient India. The wealth goddess who was hailed by elephants formed a parallel with the serpent goddess who was hailed by snakes. Manasā etymologically is a goddess who fulfils the deep desires of the mind, and Lakṣmī performs similar functions.

Five: The Yakṣī

The presence of Yakṣī cults in CKG archaeological complex is a contentious issue, because all archaeologists or scholars of ancient history claiming the CKG idols to be Yakṣīs almost always invariably indicate a watertight division between the goddess cults and the yakṣa/yakṣī cults. An idol will not be a Goddess if dubbed a Yakṣī and vice versa, it seems. But such mutual isolations would be a misreading of both the yakṣī cults and goddess cults of antiquity.

Fig 19. [“Plaque with Standing Yakṣī” as Met Museum calls this idol.](#) CKG, 100 BC.

Fig 20. “Goddess Durgā on a lotus”, as Met Museum calls this plaque. CKG, 100 BC.

There are obvious iconographic similarities between Fig. 19 and 20, and though one is called a Yakṣī and another Durgā, both these plaques could be close forerunners of the wealth goddess Lakṣmī. Some of crucial dimensions of yakṣa worship still perpetuate popular goddess cults to this day. Unbeknownst to most people, a) the gigantic size of the goddess idols (even when the main idol is small in absolute scale, the still smaller size of the attendant deities invests the iconography of the Great Goddess with a perspective of magnanimity) is an original feature from the yakṣa cults, b) tree worship on the occasion of Saptami of DurgāPūjā when the navapatrika, or a bouquet of nine sacred plants gets a ritual bath, is reminiscent of yakṣa cults, c) the splendour, wealth and boon-giving qualities repeatedly invoked in the ritual chants of the Great Goddess remind us of the conventional pursuit of wealth associated with yakṣa cults, d) the esoteric mysteries and riddles of the yakṣa cults (refer to the Yakṣa episode of Mahābhārata) can still be seen in the mysterious Tantra texts of the Goddesses, e) war victory is one of the most important aspects of yakṣa cults – refer to the revelation of Ūmā Haimavatī as Sukumar Sen recounts in *Great Goddesses* (23-24) – which is a continuous motif in the goddess traditions, f) meat and alcohol were the favourite offerings to the Yakṣas, according to Mahābhārata (Misra 3), and the same

ingredients still are used in Vāmācāra Tantra of Goddess worship, and there is this queer mix of the sacred and the profane in yakṣa cult as pointed out by Misra (vii), which is equally characteristic of Tantra, g) singing and dancing were associated with Yakṣas (Misra 3), and they continue to be ritually prescribed accompaniments in popular goddess festivals like Durgā Pujā.

Fig. 21 [CKG Plaque, 200 BC, called a Sunga Yakshi, from Musée Guimet.](#)

Yakṣīs can be gigantic and so can be the goddesses. Goddesses are often associated with sacred trees, and are bestowers of wealth, features similar to Yakṣīs. Both Goddesses and Yakṣīs can be found in esoteric locations like mountains. The story of Ūmā Haimavaṭī as narrated by Sukumar Sen in *Great Goddesses* strongly suggests that Yakṣa cults were intricately associated with the rise of the Great Goddess, as it is a Yakṣa who appears to transmit a divine message about war victory, which is then followed up by the arrival of Ūmā, the goddess of the snowy mountain (23-24). Etymologically the term Yakṣa means a swift apparition, a phantom (Misra 10), who can only be momentarily seen by the fortunate devotee.

The cult of the goddess as giver of bounties recalls yakṣī worship. Further, mammoth-sized idols are worshipped in the lived tradition of Goddess cults, Śākta Rāsa of Nabadwīpa (West Bengal) coming immediately to mind. The collection of nine plants (navapatṛika) worshipped as a part of the Saptami ritual of Durgāpujā might recall the arboreal connection of yakṣī cults. Even small plaques of the cultic feminine figures hint at a gigantic size of the deity by relative proportions, where a perspective is added by showing small-sized attendants of the deity by Her side. Thus we see the rise of the Great Goddess.

Fig 22. [Goddess of Prosperity, hailed by elephants. CKG, 200 BC. Goddess of Wealth, Lakṣmī has the same iconography of 'elephant coronation' \(Kumbhābhiseka\)](#)

The bhāva of Īśvara, or the essence of the divine, is called Aiśvarya, and this term also means wealth in Bengali which might suggest a deep-rooted religious unconscious inherited from yakṣa worship. Yakṣas are primarily wealth deities, they are the guardians of wealth in popular perceptions. Wealth deity Kubera was a Yakṣa. Wealth Goddess Lakṣmī (Lokkhi in Bengali) might have originally been a Yakṣī (Jokkhi in Bengali). Virgil's mention of the Gangaridai in his *Georgics*, where he intends to write about their military valour in letters of solid gold and ivory - "in foribus pugnam ex auro solidoque elephanto. Gangaridum faciam" (*Georgics* III 27) - indicates prosperity and by extension might suggest Yakṣic cults of wealth.

Goddesses can be Yakṣīs, and Yakṣīs Goddesses. The Jain Goddess Ambikā is explicitly called a Yakṣī in Jain theology, which means that there are no watertight demarcations between goddess domains and yakṣī domains. Later iconography of Ambikā often shows Her riding a lion, so does Ūmā Who rides a mountain lion. In *Harivaṃśa*, the Great Goddess is conceived as the first among the yakṣīs (yakṣāṇām prathamā yakṣī), as Sen observes in his *Great Goddesses* (29). As the yakṣa/yakṣī cults were later relegated to the margins by mainstream orthodox Brahminism (Misra 7), much of its insignia conveniently survived within the goddess cults.

Many features of Yakṣī worship, for example a resplendent deity, an aerial attendant, gigantic size or the grandeur of the deity – can be seen in this Chandraketugarh plaque below, where the deity is identified as "probably Sri Lakṣmī" by Met Museum.

Fig. 23 [Goddess Śrī Lakṣmī, according to Met Museum. Note the winged attendant/Vidyādhari above on right. 200 BC.CKG](#)

Such Goddesses by virtue of their gigantic size might have been war goddesses, might have adorned the banners of fortified cities (Goddess Durgā was also called Aparājītā or the unvanquished in *Arthaśāstra*, and one etymology of Durgā suggests that the Goddess was worshipped in the forts/bastions). Wealth is an obvious connection with yakṣī cults. Plants connected yakṣī cults to the natural world. One of the meanings of Prakṛti is nature, which is relevant to understand yakṣī worship.

Six: Apsarā

Some popular cultic figurine types found in Bengal in the Gangaridai period were dubbed to be apsarā or divine courtesan. A particular specimen was found at Tamluk in 1883, now in Ashmolean Museum, Oxford, commonly known as the Oxford plaque, conventionally considered to be a yakṣī by scholars as well as by the Ashmolean Museum authority, but was later given the name Pañcacūdā by some historians, primarily because of the five weapon-shaped hair-pins which adorn her headgear. But This creates a problem. Pañcacūdā of Indian mythology was not a yakṣī.

[Pañcacūdā](#) was an apsarā who was mentioned by name in the *Mahābhārata* a couple of times. She is a celestial nymph who witnesses the aerial journey of Śuka, the son of Vyāsa. Also, celestial sage Nārada has a learned conversation with Pañcacūdā on the topic of frailty of women, which is reported by Bhīṣma in the Anuśāsana parva of *Mahābhārata*. Further, we find in Purāṇic narrative that Pañcacūdā arose from the great churning of the cosmic ocean during divine quest for the nectar of immortality. Incidentally Goddess Lakṣmī Herself arose from the cosmic ocean in the same churning process.

[Fig. 24. “Oxford Plaque” from Ashmolean is “Yakṣī: Nature Spirit: A goddess adorned with heavy jewellery”. 200 BC](#)

But nothing in the iconography of the said type of Chandraketugarh figurines supports the identification with the celestial courtesan. The five weapon-shaped hairpins in the Oxford plaque do not present a very strong case, as it is not backed by any explanation of the nomenclature of Pañcacūḍā from the epic or Purāṇic narratives. Etymologically the name means five crests, or five tufts of hair (Monier-Williams). But it does not mean five hairpins or five miniscule weapons. Furthermore, in most of the plaques we see ten hairpins, and not five. Most importantly, absolutely no iconographic detail suggests that this is a courtesan. Most paradoxically, some scholars have resorted to calling such plaques Pañcacūḍā Yakṣī, which makes no sense, because the mythical Pañcacūḍā is an apsarā and is never identified with a yakṣī. Lastly, going by an overwhelming scholarly consensus, this type is a cultic *deity*, and not a courtesan.

Interestingly, the original etymology of the term apsarā is a lady who moves in water (Misra 3). In that original sense, water nymphs or mermaids were indeed present in Chandraketugarh. Further, the legendary independence of the apsarās, the patriarchal perception of women’s frailty or lack of chastity which constitutes the topic of aforementioned discussion between Nārada and Pañcacūḍā, and the cultural process of othering through the male gaze inherent in the concept of apsarā – together indicate that this otherwise casual, accidental nomenclature of Pañcacūḍā may need some serious investigations. Lastly, Apsarās are kindred to yakṣas in Vedic texts and share some striking commonalities (Misra 3).

[Fig. 25. So-called mermaid plaque, CKG, 200 BC.](#)

Seven: The Fish & the Goddess

Fish symbols are numerous and manifold in the Harappan civilization. In some cases, the fish can represent a water deity, as Asko Parpola maintains by illustrating some parallels with Mesopotamian civilization where the fish symbolised an aquatic deity. Fish symbols are prominent in the potteries of Pandu Rajar Dhibi (PRD), but are rare in Chandraketugarh (CKG), where we do not see any prominent water deity. But we have detected a few cultic plaques where a female figurine has crop-shaped hairpins, and holds a pair of fishes in one of her hands. She can be called Dhānyamatsyā, or the Goddess of rice and fish, in other words, the Goddess who gives food. The later theology of Annapūrṇa can provide us with some reference point. This is not just a Matsya-Lakṣmī or a piscine Lakṣmī figure who represents abundance through the insignia of fish. This is more importantly a nourishment deity who is seen to embody the staple diet of coastal Bengal. Ultimately this is a Maternal deity, the primal nurturing source for all children. A pair of Hilsa fishes are still worshipped on the occasion of Saraswatī Pūjā in eastern Bengal, which is reminiscent of archaic piscine cults of a river deity. Indian myths of the great deluge mention the fish deity as a guardian protector.

Fig. 26. [Left, from Santa Barbara Museum of Art, California.](#) [Right, from Victoria and Albert Museum, London](#)

Eight: Mother with Baby/Mother of God

The motif of the mother with child can be found very prominently in the Harappan civilization, and in Shereen Ratnagar's book *The Magic in the Image*, we can see that the motif 'mother with child' constituted the largest number of such clay idols of Harappan world. These mother-with-baby figurines were used in cultic practices, fertility rites, or in ceremonies which were forerunners of vrata rituals (where such clay idols are made, and then are discarded after the ritual is performed).

Fig. 27. (left) Harappan Mother with baby, Mehrgarh, 2800 BC. (centre) Gangaridai Mother with baby, CKG, 200 BC. (right) Mother of God? Note how the baby looks significantly 'mature'. CKG, 200 BC. Collection from Musée Guimet

We witness the resurfacing of this tradition of mother-with-child figurines in Chandraketugarh (CKG), which proves that it reemerged as a very important cult during the Gangaridai era. Today, *Ṣaṣṭhī* is often represented in this way, as the maternal goddess holding a baby in her lap. In Buddhist Tantra, renowned Goddess *Hāritī* had a similar iconography. Many Goddesses in the Pāla period have this maternal iconography, *Manasā* during this age is very prominently seen in most of Her idols holding a baby. In Tarapith (*Tārāpīṭh*) temple of Bengal, Goddess *Tārā* is worshipped in a Pāla-Sena period icon of Mother with a newborn, which is popularly known to the priests and devotees as *brahmaśilā*. The theology latent in such an iconography obviously celebrates the feminine principle as first cause of creation, or *Prakṛti Jagadkāraṇa*. But as the last example shows, this baby could be a deity itself, and as the Mother of the universe, She could be contemplated as the Mother of God.

Nine: One-Horned Goddess

A mysterious one-horned figurine of CKG tempts us to imagine some forgotten connections with the all-pervasive unicorn of the Harappan world! This female figurine can also be an early form of *Ekānaṃśā*, a very popular goddess in antiquity, later subsumed into the Vaishnava pantheon. The single horn in her headgear might signify singularity and monism. Etymologically the term *Ekānaṃśā* means one who is single (*ekā*) and not shared (*an-āṃśā*), that is, who is without consort. She is later appropriated by Vaiṣṇavism as the sister of *Kṛṣṇa*. It is interesting to note that *ekaśṛṅga*, or one-horned is one of the epithets of *Viṣṇu* in Hindu mythology, and *Kṛṣṇa* calls himself *ekaśṛṅga* in *Mahābhārata*. Michel Danino believes that this may be an allusion to the cult of the Harappan unicorn (238). A pale shadow of the mighty *Ekānaṃśā* who was once a supreme deity, can still be seen in the Goddess *Subhadrā* of Vaiṣṇavism, as Sen observes in *Great Goddesses* (30).

Fig. 28. (left) One-horned figurine called a “fertility figure”. She holds a bird in the left hand, and some fruits in the right hand. Asian Art Museum, San Francisco. (centre) Another Plaque of the same figurine. Honolulu Academy of Arts. (right) Another plaque of the same figurine, but this time being teased by a playful figure (brother?). Met Museum.

Conclusion

This article is an attempt to reconstruct the archaic theology of terracotta plaques and figurines from early Bengal within the context of goddess religions, with cross-references to the Harappan world. “Worship of Mother Goddess in terracotta figurines” maintains K N Dikshit, “continued to be the main visible link between the main Indus culture and the Gangetic culture of historical date” (36). Living Hinduism today can be traced back to the Harappan civilization, Atul Sur comments (*Sindhu Sabhyatar Swarupa O Samasya* 38). These archaic cults often had common motifs, i.e. sacred plants. They predate Harappan era and transcend iconic depictions. [J M Kenoyer](#) speaks of stone age Kālī temple(s) in central India, dating back to 11000 years, where the Goddess is worshipped as an aniconic stone, bearing a strong resemblance to the female generative organ. Many millennia later, the ancient Indian concept of *Yoni* arose, as the primordial matter, as the first cause of creation of universe, Prakṛti Jagadkāraṇa, which I discussed in my article on Śūdrakās Mṛcchakaṭika, titled “The Gambler in the Empty Temple”.

Fig. 30. [Yoni Stone Worshipped as Kālī from the paleolithic shrine](#) in Baghor, Central India

The Primordial Matter causing of creation of the universe is contemplated in feminine form as the unspeakable (avyaktā), the primordial (ādyā), the eternal (nityā) – in popular imagination, the Mother Goddess. Though we limited ourselves to the iconology and theology of the goddess cults, the feminine principle of creation is timeless and formless. Let us fittingly conclude this article with an image of this aniconic roundel from [CKG, 200 BC](#) which was probably a cultic representation of the goddess.

Bibliography

- Bhattacharya, Hangsarayan. *Hinduder Debdebi*. Kolkata: Firma KLM, 1386 (Bengali Year).
- Chattopadhyay, Debiprasad. *Bharatiya Darshan*. Kolkata: NBA, 2012.
- Chattopadhyay, Rupendrakumar, Satyasourav Jana & Dipanwita Sarkar. "Mahiṣasuramardini: Ekti Prāsongik Ālocona" in Debashish Saha & Aditya Mukhopadhyay (eds). *Debī Durgā Swarūp O Sandhān*. Kolkata: Nandita, 2013. pp127-145.
- Danino, Michel. *The Lost River*. New Delhi: Penguin, 2010.
- Dasgupta, Paresh Chandra. *The Excavations at Pandu Rajar Dhibi*. Kolkata: Directorate of Archaeology, West Bengal, 1962.
- Dasgupta, Sasibhusan. *Bharater Sakti Sādhana O Sakta Sahitya*. Kolkata: Sahitya Samsad, 1387 (Bengali Year).
- Dasgupta, Tamal. "Bangalir Bismrito Oti". *Shoptodina* 9.2.2023 <<https://wp.me/p9ibuA-NG>>
- . "Ma Kālir Utthan". *Shoptodina* 6.1.2020. <<https://wp.me/p9ibuA-iQ>>
- . "The Gambler in the Empty Temple". *Śūdrakās Mṛcchakaṭikam*. Ed. Saptarshi Mallick. Bolpur: Birujatio Sahitya Sammiloni, 2022. pp 361-392
- Dikshit, K. N. *Prehistoric Civilization of the Indus Valley*. Madras: Madras University Press, 1939
- Erndl, Kathleen, *Victory to the Mother*. New York: OUP, 1993. Ebook from Amazon Kindle.
- Kenoyer, J. M. "An Upper Paleolithic Shrine in India?". *Antiquity*, LVII, 1983.
- Misra, Ram Nath. *Yaksha Cult and Iconography*. New Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal, 1981.
- Parpola, Asko. *The Roots of Hinduism*. New York: OUP, 2015.
- Ratnagar, Shereen. *The Magic in the Image*. New Delhi: Manohar, 2018.
- Shin, Jae-Eun. *Change, Continuity and Complexity: The Mahāvīdyās in East Indian Śākta Traditions*. New York: Routledge, 2018.
- Sen, Sukumar. *Probandho Sonkolon*, Vol.3. Kolkata: Ananda, 2017.
- . *The Great Goddesses of Indie Tradition*. Kolkata: Papyrus, 1983
- . "Mahādevī Nityā". *Sarpa-Sanskriti O Manasā*. Eds. Anjan Sen & Sk. Maqbool Islam. Kolkata: Bangiya Sahitya Samsad, 2012.
- Sengupta, Gautam et al (eds). *Eloquent Earth*. Kolkata: Directorate of Archaeology, 2007.
- Sur, Atul. *Bangla O Bangalir Biborton*. Kolkata: Sahitya Lok, 2012.
- . *Sindhu Sabhyatar Swarupa O Samasya*. Kolkata: Ujjwal Sahitya Mandir, 1357 (Bengali Year).